

Mitigating phytotoxicity of hydrothermal liquefaction hydrochar toward potential agricultural applications

Gabriel F. Batista^{*}, Andrea Kruse, Gero C. Becker

University of Hohenheim, Institute of Agricultural Engineering, Department of Conversion Technologies of Biobased Resources, Garbenstr. 9, 70599 Stuttgart, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Valorizing hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) by-products is essential to improve process sustainability and support its industrial-scale implementation. However, the direct agricultural application of HTL-derived hydrochar remains limited due to reported phytotoxic effects. By studying and mitigating phytotoxicity, this work evaluates the potential suitability for agricultural use of hydrochar, the solid by-product from continuous HTL of a 50/50 wt. % cattle manure and wheat straw mixture at 325 °C, separated with an in-line filter. Phytotoxicity was assessed using seed germination assays with Barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) and Cress (*Lepidium sativum*) seeds. Two hydrochar post-treatments, washing (hydrochloric acid and water) and pyrolysis (300 °C and 500 °C), were examined to mitigate hydrochar phytotoxicity. Raw HTL-hydrochar significantly hindered plant growth, reducing the root lengths of barley and cress by 37 % and 70 %, respectively, compared to the control. Water-washed post-treatment eliminated hydrochar phytotoxicity and enhanced Barley root growth by 42 % compared to control at a 15 ton ha⁻¹ application rate, indicating a possible growth-stimulating effect. Pyrolysis also mitigated hydrochar phytotoxic effects, with cress root lengths statistically similar to the control. No uptake of heavy metals by the plants were observed in the germination assays. These results suggest that phytotoxicity originates from water-soluble organic compounds, likely phenols, short-chain organic acids and aldehydes, produced during HTL process and adsorbed in the hydrochar surface. The novelty of this work lies in demonstrating the complete removal of phytotoxicity from HTL hydrochar using technologically mature and scalable post-treatments. Therefore, a barrier to hydrochar valorization is removed, enabling further investigations into agronomic applications. This work contributes to a circular biomass valorization strategy.

List of Abbreviations

ANOVA Analysis of Variance
DOC Dissolved Organic Carbon
E.C. Electrical Conductivity
ENS Extracted Nutrient Solution
FAO Food and Agriculture Organization
F.C. Fixed Carbon
GC-MS/MS Gas Chromatography-Tandem Mass Spectrometry
GHG Greenhouse gases
GR Germination Rate
HC Hydrochar
HCl Hydrochloric acid
HTC-HC Hydrothermal Carbonization Hydrochar
HTL Hydrothermal Liquefaction
HTL-Char Hydrothermal Liquefaction Hydrochar

LOD Limit of Detection
PAHs Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
PNNL Pacific Northwest National Laboratory
RFW Relative Fresh Weight
RL Root Length
RRI Relative Root Index
VM Volatile Matter

1. Introduction

Once considered waste, residual biomass is now recognized as a valuable resource and can potentially mitigate about 200 million tons of CO₂ emissions annually (Rosa et al., 2021). Effective management of biomass can directly contribute to sustainable agriculture, by reducing pollution, closing nutrient cycles, producing sustainable fertilizers and enhancing soil health. In this framework, intelligent management and

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail address: gabriel.batista@uni-hohenheim.de (G.F. Batista).

use of biomass are key aspects in our society (Gupta et al., 2022). Animal manure is one of the most widely generated organic waste products, with an annual production of approximately 1.4 billion tons in Europe. If not properly managed, the manure poses a significant environmental threat (Köninger et al., 2021). Most of the manure is processed through anaerobic digestion or composting. However, both methods require long processing times. Thus, hydrothermal liquefaction (HTL) of manure is emerging as a promising thermochemical process for biomass valorization (Liu et al., 2023).

In agricultural systems, cattle manure and cereal straw are commonly co-produced, particularly in mixed crop–livestock farms. The co-processing of these residues has attracted increasing interest as a relevant waste management strategy. Previous studies (dos Passos et al., 2022) have demonstrated synergistic effects during co-HTL of these feedstocks compared to processing each individually, resulting in improved carbon conversion, biocrude yield, and quality.

HTL is a process that uses wet feedstocks with a water content of 70 wt. % or more to produce mainly biocrude, which can be further upgraded into fuels and other valuable chemicals (Kruse et al., 2013). The usage of wet feedstock significantly reduces the cost of the process, compared to other thermochemical conversions, as the energy-intensive drying step is avoided (Peterson et al., 2008). The HTL operates at high temperatures (280–374°C) and pressures (10 to 25 MPa), with short to moderate residence times in the order of minutes (Rivas-Arrieta et al., 2024). HTL is known for its energy and carbon efficiency. Typically, in the HTL process, more than 70 % of the carbon is recovered from the feedstock in its product streams. The HTL process generates four main product fractions: biocrude (bio-oil), an aqueous, a gaseous, and a solid phase named HTL-hydrochar (HTL-Char). Among these products, HTL-Char is by far the most understudied one, although it can represent up to 25 % of the process yield on a mass basis (Rivas-Arrieta et al., 2024, Kruse and Dahmen, 2015).

To promote the large-scale commercialization of HTL, valorizing the side streams into products with market value is essential. For a long time, the HTL-Char was neglected and considered an undesired side product (Middleton-Smith et al., 2023). Therefore, there is a need to develop value chains for this solid by-product, and a significant knowledge gap exists in understanding the characteristics and applications of HTL-Char. In addition, Rivas-Arrieta et al. (2024) (Rivas-Arrieta et al., 2024) proved that HTL-Char produced from batch HTL reactors has different properties compared to HTL-Char produced in continuous HTL reactors coupled with an in-line separator, using the same feedstock and operational parameters for both modes of operation. HTL-Char produced in a continuous reactor had a higher ash content, lower carbon content, and reduced formation of secondary char than its counterpart produced from batch reactors. Additionally, continuous HTL-Char exhibited a lower abundance of nitrogenated and oxygenated compounds, and a higher fraction of alkanes and alkenes. These differences are attributed to fundamental variations in heat and residence time distribution, and phase separation behavior between batch and continuous HTL systems (Rivas-Arrieta et al., 2024). In continuous reactors with in-line filtration, solids can be removed earlier from the reacting medium, limiting secondary char formation from biocrude polymerization and limiting oil adsorption on the char surface. These changes in physicochemical properties may influence HTL-Char's suitability for various applications.

HTL-Char is a product composed primarily of carbon (up to 60 wt. %), along with a high concentration of nutrients, as the majority of the feedstock's inorganic components are retained in the solid phase (up to 70 wt.%) (Ponnusamy et al., 2020, Pecchi et al., 2023). The HTL process parameters and the feedstock used heavily influence the characteristics of the HTL-Char. Recent studies have explored its potential as a fuel material (Zheng et al., 2015), nutrient recovery (Ovsyannikova et al., 2021), production of adsorbents (Leng et al., 2015), and as a precursor for fertilizers, such as struvite (Ovsyannikova et al., 2020, Shukla et al., 2024, Sharma et al., 2025).

As there is limited literature related to HTL-Char application in agriculture, a comparison can be made with other carbonaceous materials. A similar material, hydrochar produced from hydrothermal carbonization (HTC-HC), has been widely studied for its applications in soil (Bargmann et al., 2013, Bona et al., 2023, Cervera-Mata et al., 2021). Both HTL-Char and HTC-HC are carbon-rich solids that can potentially serve as soil amendments. However, HTC-HC and HTL-Char are fundamentally different materials, due to distinct process conditions and product distribution. HTC typically operates at 180–250°C with autogenous pressure and yields as a main product the solid fraction (Román et al., 2018). Conversely, HTL is performed at higher temperatures and pressures, and it is optimized for biocrude production. Therefore, HTL-Char typically contains higher concentrations of inorganic compounds, heavy metals and may retain oil residues on its surface, which could present a potential risk to plants (Pecchi et al., 2023, Lachos-Perez et al., 2022). These differences are relevant for agricultural applications, as they affect phytotoxicity, carbon fixation potential and nutrient availability.

Many studies have observed that native HTC-HC are phytotoxic to plants, primarily due to the formation of several toxic compounds formed or set free during hydrothermal reactions, including phenols, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), organic acids, and aldehydes (Celletti et al., 2021, Puccini et al., 2018, Yuan et al., 2024, Li et al., 2023). A review by Karatas et al. (2022) (Karatas et al., 2022) compiled many HTC-HC phytotoxicity studies, and it was concluded that the main strategies to reduce the general phytotoxicity of these materials are aging (Busch et al., 2013), washing (Wu et al., 2021), co-composting (Bona et al., 2022) and a further thermal treatment, as pyrolysis (Hitzl et al., 2018). However, due to significant differences in process conditions (temperature, pressure, residence time, and product composition), HTC and HTL-derived hydrochars are different materials.

Some literature points out the HTL-Char's potential application as a soil amendment (Mohan et al., 2025); however, to the authors' knowledge, there is a minimal number of studies that have yet evaluated the direct use of HTL-Char in agriculture. One of the few studies evaluating the HTL-Char agricultural potential was performed by Sharma et al. (2025) (Sharma et al., 2025). They produced HTL-Char using biogas digestate as feedstock in a continuous HTL pilot plant. Significant challenges included high concentrations of chromium (Cr), nickel (Ni), and PAHs in the HTL-Char, all exceeding the limits set by Danish legislation. The germination assays with *Lepidium sativum* showed that HTL-Char application rates above 5 % or 10 % adversely affected germination. However, the study did not provide information on plant development parameters such as root length or biomass, nor did it explore treatments to improve the agronomic properties of HTL-Char.

Therefore, HTL-Char must be carefully evaluated for its toxicity to plants and soil biota before applying this material for agricultural purposes, as it can contain several toxic organic substances and a high concentration of heavy metals, and those substances are potential sources of phytotoxicity (Ponnusamy et al., 2020, Sharma et al., 2025). If the potential of HTL-Char for soil amendment is proven, it could significantly enhance the HTL process by creating a new valuable product, potentially increasing process profitability and improving the process's greenhouse gas (GHG) balance through carbon sequestration.

Given the above-mentioned context, this study addresses the research gap in the agricultural application of HTL-Char produced from a pilot-scale continuous HTL plant processing a mixture of cattle manure and wheat straw. It is important to note that the objective of this study is not to produce char via HTL, but rather to valorize the solid hydrochar by-product from HTL. Thus, the novelty of this work lies in the assessment of this understudied material for agricultural use, and the evaluation of strategies to improve HTL-Char agricultural properties and mitigate phytotoxicity. Two germination assays will be conducted to assess the phytotoxicity of HTL-Char and identify potential sources of adverse effects on plants. This work aims to answer the following research questions: (1) Is HTL-Char produced from the continuous co-

HTL of a cattle manure/wheat straw mixture phytotoxic? (2) What are the potential sources of phytotoxicity? (3) Which post-treatment methodologies are effective in mitigating the phytotoxicity of HTL-Char? By answering these questions, this paper aims to provide a foundation for future research involving HTL-Char in agricultural applications.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. HTL-Char production and characterization

The HTL-Char sample originated from the pilot-scale HTL plant at Aarhus University. A comprehensive description of the HTL process and pilot plant can be found in this work (Anastasakis et al., 2018). In brief, a 50 % mixture of cattle manure and wheat straw, with a total dry matter content of approximately 11 %, was pumped into the continuous HTL reactor. This feedstock mixture was selected due to the reported synergistic effects in HTL (dos Passos et al., 2022). The HTL plant operated at 325°C and 17 MPa, with an average residence time of approximately 15 minutes. The resulting solid was recovered using an in-line separation settler. Solids leave the reactor as a slurry-like mixture of solids, process water, and some residual oil fraction, as biocrude components can be adsorbed in the hydrochar matrix. While further biocrude recovery from the hydrochar might be possible, in this study, the hydrochar was analyzed in the form directly obtained from the pilot-scale HTL process. The product was centrifuged, then dried at 105°C, ground to a particle size that can pass through a 10-mm mesh and further analyzed. This sample was named HTL-HC. The HTL-HC yield was calculated relative to the dry feedstock input and is reported on a dry-basis.

The HTL-HC was thoroughly characterized. Proximate analysis (volatile matter (VM), ash and fixed carbon (FC)) was performed according to the standards DIN EN 51720:2001-03 (Testing of solid fuels – Determination of volatile matter content 2001), and DIN 51719:1997-07 (Testing of solid fuels – Solid mineral fuels – Determination of ash content 1997). The FC content was calculated according to Eq. (1) (Cao et al., 2019). Elemental analysis (C, H, N, S) was conducted using an elemental analyzer (Eurovector S.P.A., Milano, Italy). The concentration of O (wt.%) was calculated according to Eq. (2). Atomic ratios (H/C) and (O/C) were also determined.

$$FC(d.b. wt.%) = 100\% - VM(d.b. wt.%) - Ash(d.b. wt.%) \quad (1)$$

$$O(wt.%) = 100\% - C(wt.%) - H(wt.%) - N(wt.%) - S(wt.%) - Ash(wt.%) \quad (2)$$

The solids were digested as described in the reference (Ovsyannikova et al., 2020). Subsequently, the concentration of inorganic elements (Ca, Cd, Cr, Cu, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, Na, Ni, P, Pb, and Zn) was determined by Inductively Coupled Plasma - Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES), Agilent, 715 ES emission spectrometer. The pH was determined according to the standard DIN ISO 10390 (Soil, treated biowaste and sludge – Determination of pH (ISO 10390:2021) 2022). Electric conductivity (E.C.) was determined in a solid-to-deionized water ratio of 1:5 (Suarez et al., 2023). The same methods and analytical techniques were used to characterize the HTL-derived solids after post-treatment, produced during this work.

The concentrations of PAHs in the materials were determined using a modified procedure based on DIN EN 17503:2022-08 (Soil, sludge, treated biowaste and waste - Determination of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) 2022). Briefly, PAHs were extracted from the solids using accelerated solvent extraction with n-hexane and acetone (1:1, v/v) as the extraction solvents. The resulting extracts were concentrated to 2 mL before analysis. Quantification of PAHs was performed by gas chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry (GC-MS/MS) using an Agilent 7890B gas chromatograph coupled to an Agilent 7000D triple quadrupole mass spectrometer.

2.2. HTL-HC post-treatments

Two post-treatments were performed before applying the HTL-HC in phytotoxicity trials. In total, four new HTL-HC-derived materials were generated. These post-treatments, described in sections 2.2.1 and 2.2.2, aim to improve the HTL-HC properties and reduce the material's phytotoxicity.

2.2.1. Water and acidic washing

Two washing agents were used for post-treatment: deionized water or a 1.0 mol L⁻¹ hydrochloric acid (HCl) solution (30 % w/v, Supelco). The washing process employed a solid-to-liquid mass ratio of 1:33, adapted from reported washing protocols (Liu et al., 2022, Jin et al., 2022). For every washing agent, three replicates were performed. The HTL-HC and liquid were mixed and agitated at room temperature for 4 h at 480 rpm. After agitation, the samples were vacuum filtered using a 0.34 mm Whatman filter paper. For the acid-washed sample, the solids were thoroughly rinsed with distilled water until the supernatant reached a neutral pH. The post-treated HTL-HC samples were then dried overnight in an oven at 105°C. The resulting samples were designated as HTL-HC-WW for the water-washed and HTL-HC-AW for the acid-washed material.

2.2.2. Pyrolysis process

The HTL-HC was pyrolyzed in a muffle oven coupled with a constant nitrogen gas flow to ensure an oxygen-free atmosphere. Approximately 10 g of ground HTL-HC was placed into an 80 mm diameter alumina crucible (VWR, Germany) covered with a lid, and the crucible was placed into a 2 L stainless-steel box. Two replicates were performed for every pyrolysis temperature. Before pyrolysis, nitrogen was flushed into the pyrolysis box. The pyrolysis was carried out at a heating rate of 300°C h⁻¹, with a maximum temperature of 300°C or 500 °C, a residence time of 2 h, and a N₂ flow of 5 L min⁻¹. After the reaction time, the samples were allowed to cool to room temperature, maintaining a constant nitrogen flow. The resulting biochars were designated as PY-300-HTL and PY-500-HTL for the materials pyrolyzed at 300°C and 500°C, respectively.

2.3. Phytotoxicity trials

Two phytotoxicity assays were performed with the samples. As a result, the germination rate (GR), relative root index (RRI), and relative fresh weight (RFW) were evaluated after the germination assays. In the first test, named as Mason jar trials, the solids were directly mixed with an inert growing medium (sand) to simulate agricultural field applications, and applied for the germination of Barley seeds (Bargmann et al., 2013). Barley seeds are not sensitive to salt stress (Busch et al., 2012). For the second assay, named as Petri dish trials, the hydrochar liquid extract was applied to the growth media. *Lepidium sativum* seeds were used in this test, as they are more sensitive to salt stress (Nouri and Haddioui, 2021). The second test aimed to investigate the possible compounds responsible for phytotoxicity by analyzing the properties of the liquid extract.

2.3.1. Mason jar trials - Direct solid application

The first test utilized a mixture of HTL-Char and quartz sand as growing media to evaluate the phytotoxicity effects of the materials on the germination of Barley seeds (*Hordeum Vulgare*), following an adapted methodology proposed by Bargmann et al. (2013) (Bargmann et al., 2013, Busch et al., 2012, Bouqbis et al., 2017). The 10-day experiment was conducted in 1 L Mason jars, which were open. Each jar was filled with 800 g of a mixture of sand and HTL-HC, respecting the application ratios of 15 or 30 ton ha⁻¹ of char, considering a soil depth of 15 cm. The sand was pre-treated by washing, drying, and heating at 600 °C for 3 h. After mixing, the growing media was saturated with 60 % of WHC using deionized water, and 20 Barley seeds were introduced to

each jar. The experiments were carried out in duplicate ($n = 2$), using two controls (only sand) for each batch. In total, five experimental batches were carried out.

The jars were then transferred to a climate-controlled room maintained at 24 ± 1 °C with a 12-hour light/dark cycle. On days 4 and 7, 10 mL of deionized water was added to the jars. On the 10th day of the experiment, each plant was removed from the jars, extensively washed with deionized water and dried using a paper towel. The fresh weight was measured. The GR and root length were determined using the software ImageJ Version 1.54j.

GR was calculated according to Eq. (3) (BS EN 2011).

$$GR(\%) = \frac{\sum \frac{GS_i(\text{Jar } i)}{TSC}}{\sum TSC} * 100 \quad (3)$$

Where:

GS_i = Germinated seeds on the jar i , TSC = Total seeds count on the jar, and GR (%) = Germination rate.

RRI was calculated according to Eq.s 4 and 5 (BS EN 2011).

$$ARLP = \frac{\sum \left(\frac{RL}{GS} \right)}{\text{NumberofJars}} \quad (4)$$

$$RRI(\%) = \frac{\sum \frac{ARLP(\text{Jar } i)}{ARLP(\text{control})}}{\text{NumberofJars}} * 100 \quad (5)$$

Where:

RL = Root length (cm), ARLP = Average root length per jar (cm), and RRI (%) = Relative root index related to the control (%).

RFW was calculated according to Eq. (6).

$$RFW(\%) = \frac{\sum (PFW(\text{Jar } i))}{\sum (PFW(\text{Control Jar}))} * 100 \quad (6)$$

Where:

PFW = Plant fresh weight (mg).

Since the germination experiments were divided into five batches, direct comparisons of root and stem lengths and plant weight between plants from different batches are not feasible, as uncontrolled external factors could have influenced plant growth. Therefore, the RRI and RFW were used, as these variables were calculated relative to the control treatment within each batch. This allows comparison across different batches.

The plants were then dried at 60 °C for 72 h, and the dry weight was determined. The dried plants were analyzed via ICP-OES to determine the uptake of inorganic elements.

2.3.2. Petri dish trials – nutrient solution extraction

The second phytotoxicity assay was performed using the nutrient extract method, applied to Petri dishes containing seeds of cress (*Lepidium Sativum*), following the BS EN 16086-2:2011 standard (BS EN 2011) and adapted from the literature (Hitzl et al., 2018, BS EN 2011, Bahcivanji et al., 2020). The hydrochar liquid extract was obtained using the nutrient extraction method. For this method, 20.0 g of hydrochar were mixed with 200 mL of a standard nutrient solution. The chemical composition of the standard nutrient solution can be found in Supplementary Table S1. The mixture was agitated for 4 h and then vacuum-filtered using a 0.34 mm Whatman filter paper. The extracted nutrient solution (ENS) was used for the Petri dish tests, and the spent solid was disposed. A 12 cm square Petri dish was filled with perlite and covered with filter paper, which was wetted with 50 mL of the ENS. Then, 10 cress seeds were evenly positioned on top of the filter paper. The petri dishes were closed and sealed with parafilm. Each treatment test was conducted in triplicate ($n = 3$), alongside a quadruplicate control.

The Petri dishes were incubated horizontally at an angle of 80° in a

climate chamber at a constant temperature of 24 ± 1 °C for 72 h in complete darkness. After incubation, the germinated seeds and root lengths were measured using ImageJ software, version 1.54j. The GR was calculated according to Eq. (3), and the root length (RL) was directly compared among treatments, since all experiments were conducted in the same batch.

The standard nutrient solution and ENS were characterized to identify potential sources of phytotoxicity. The concentrations of inorganic elements were analyzed via ICP-OES. The pH and E.C. were determined using a HACH HQ40d multi-equipment. Dissolved organic carbon (DOC), phenolic compounds and ammonium (NH_4^+) were determined using HACH cuvette tests LCK380, LCK345 and LCK303, respectively, in the spectral photometer DR6000 (HACH LANGE GmbH, Düsseldorf, Germany).

2.4. Data analysis

All results are presented as means of the replicates \pm standard deviation. For the GR, RFW and RRI, the residuals were tested for homogeneity of variance and normal distribution. Residuals that did not fit these criteria were not evaluated. A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed, followed by a comparison of means (Tukey's test) with the statistical software R Version 6.45 (CoHort, Berkeley, CA, USA). Significant means differences ($p < 0.05$) are indicated by different letters. Exact p-values from Tukey's post hoc tests for all pairwise comparisons are provided in the Supplementary Tables S2-S4.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of the HTL hydrochar and derived materials

The data reported in Table 1 shows the main chemical characteristics of the feedstock used in the HTL experiment, and the HTL-HC samples.

The raw HTL-HC yield obtained from the continuous HTL process was approximately 5 wt.% on a dry feedstock basis. Washing treatments resulted in minor mass losses, with yields of 96.7 wt.% and 92.6 wt.% for HTL-HC-WW and HTL-HC-AW, respectively, indicating limited removal of soluble components. In contrast, pyrolysis presented greater mass losses, particularly at 500 °C. The pyrolysis at 300 °C preserved most of the solid fraction (94.3 wt.%), while pyrolysis at 500 °C reduced the yield to 68.8 wt.%, reflecting the thermal decomposition of labile organic compounds.

In the context of applying these materials as soil amendments, the pH is a critical factor influencing soil chemistry and fertility, affecting nutrient mobility and bioavailability (Neina, 2019). The pH of the HTL-HC and washed chars had a slightly acidic pH ranging from 6.5 to 6.9, lower than the initial feedstocks pH. This pH reduction is attributed to the production of acidic compounds during HTL, as sugars are decomposed in organic acids (Kruse et al., 2013). Thereby, these materials could be potential amendments for alkaline soils. In contrast, the pyrolysis shifted the material pH from slightly acidic towards alkaline, with a pH range of 7.4 -8.4. The increase in pH is consistent with findings from different authors, where the char produced through pyrolysis tends to have a higher pH due to enrichment of alkali and alkaline earth metals in the ash fraction (Luo et al., 2024, Hossain et al., 2011). When those materials are applied to soil, the alkaline pH could increase soil pH, causing a reduction in the solubility and bioavailability of nutrients. Therefore, the application of this material should be closely managed with soil pH monitoring to avoid adverse effects (Neina, 2019, Jeffery et al., 2011).

The E.C. of the HTL-HC was the highest among the tested materials at 3.42 ± 0.06 mS cm^{-1} . This elevated E.C. indicates high salinity from the ash content in the char. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) classification (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations 2018), this E.C. value categorizes the material as capable of generating slightly saline soils (E.C. between 2.0 and 4.0 mS cm^{-1}).

Table 1
Physicochemical properties of the feedstock, HTL-HC and post-treated HTL-HC.

	Manure	Straw	HTL-HC	HTL-HC-WW	HTL-HC-AW	PY-300-HTL	PY-500-HTL
Yield (wt.%)	-	-	5	96.7	92.6	94.3	68.8
VM (wt.%)	70.7	62.9	38.9	35.3	37.0	34.7	22.3
Ash (wt.%)	10.4	4.3	19.7	19.1	16.6	21.0	27.4
FC (wt.%)	18.9	32.8	14.4	45.6	46.4	44.3	50.3
C (wt.%)	43.9	44.9	62.3	61.5	64.1	60.0	61.6
H (wt.%)	6.0	6.3	5.4	4.9	5.1	4.1	2.5
N (wt.%)	2.6	0.4	2.9	3.0	3.1	2.7	2.9
S (wt.%)	0.5	0.0	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.0	0.0
O (wt.%)	46.4	44.5	9.3	11.2	10.9	12.3	5.6
pH	7.8	6.9	6.6	6.9	6.5	7.4	8.4
E.C. (mS/cm)	1.1	0.9	3.4	0.9	1.0	2.0	1.8
∑16 EPA PAHS (mg/kg)	n.d.	n.d.	4.0	5.3	5.4	5.9	1.4
Ca (g/kg)	18.1	3.8	26.8	29.0	20.2	28.5	36.8
Fe (g/kg)	0.9	0.2	2.5	2.5	2.4	2.5	2.9
K (g/kg)	33.9	11.2	6.5	3.7	2.1	6.4	6.8
Mg (g/kg)	7.9	0.6	11.4	13.3	12.8	11.0	18.5
Na (g/kg)	9.0	0.4	3.8	2.4	1.3	4.2	4.5
P (g/kg)	8.2	0.5	13.8	14.8	10.5	14.0	17.1
Cd (mg/kg)	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD
Cr (mg/kg)	3.2	9.5	150.1	139.1	137.2	152.3	173.0
Cu (mg/kg)	34.4	1.7	70.8	63.7	67.4	68.9	83.8
Mn (mg/kg)	184	21.8	252.2	262.1	202.2	256.7	333.9
Ni (mg/kg)	4.0	0.9	72.5	74.4	64.5	75.2	97.9
Pb (mg/kg)	0.7	< LOD	1.4	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD
Zn (mg/kg)	152	10.3	272.9	305.5	268.0	277.0	296.6

All data show a standard deviation $\leq 10\%$; $n = 2$; n.d. = not determined; LOD = Limit of detection = 0.25 mg kg^{-1}

The increasing degree of salinization in soils could be harmful to some plant species (Hechmi et al., 2020). The washing protocol reduced the E. C. of char to 0.9 and 1.0 mS cm^{-1} . The reduction is attributed to the effective solvation of salt ions during the washing process, as evidenced by the decrease in Na concentration in the washed materials compared to the HTL-HC. Similarly, a reduction in E.C. was observed in the pyrolyzed materials, with E.C. values ranging from 1.8 to 2.0 mS cm^{-1} . This decrease in E.C. after pyrolysis could be related to the immobilization of free ions during thermal treatment.

The total C content of all hydrochars ranged from 60.0 to 64.1 %. All materials had a higher C content than the feedstocks. The Van Krevelen diagram of the materials can be found in Supplementary Fig. 1. The increase in carbon content confirms that carbonization occurred during the HTL process. These values are typical within hydrochars from HTL of manure (Chen et al., 2018), and higher than for other feedstocks such as sludge or microalgae (Middleton-Smith et al., 2023). The thermal treatment did not significantly change the carbon content among the materials. For PY-300-HTL, this is attributed to the relatively low temperature, which falls within the range of torrefaction. Since carbon is the most abundant element in HTL-HC, this material has a significant potential to sequester carbon in soil systems and contribute to a negative

emission HTL process.

Among the carbonaceous compounds present in hydrochar, the PAHs are among the primary substances of concern, as they are hazardous to the environment. In the HTL-HC and post-treated materials analyzed in this study, the total concentration of the 16 EPA-PAHs ranged from 1.4 to 5.9 mg kg^{-1} . These values fall below the threshold specified by the European Biochar Certificate (EBC) guidelines, of $6.0 \pm 2.4 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$. By contrast, Sharma et al. (2025) (Sharma et al., 2025) reported PAHs concentrations exceeding 6.0 mg kg^{-1} in HTL solids derived from digestate, which did not comply with the EBC requirements. This comparison highlights how differences in feedstock characteristics and HTL reactor configurations can influence the concentration of organic contaminants in HTL-Char.

Washing and pyrolyzing the HC reduced VM from 38.9% to 22.3% for HTL-HC and PY-500-HTL, respectively. The reduction of VM on the post-treated materials caused an increase in the FC fraction. Higher FC in carbonaceous materials is related to higher long-term carbon capture and storage potential, as these materials are more resistant to biological degradation, offering higher stability for longer time periods (Crombie et al., 2013, Leng et al., 2019).

HTL-HC has an inorganic profile primarily composed of essential macronutrient elements such as Ca, P, K and Mg. Together, these elements constitute 5.8 % of the total material mass and 29.7 % of the ash mass. These nutrients are required for plant growth, and their high concentration underscores the potential of HTL-HC to serve as a sustainable alternative to fossil-based fertilizers (Rivas-Arrieta et al., 2024, Ponnusamy et al., 2020).

The HTL-HC ash content was 19.7 %. The obtained concentration of the ash in the solid product of HTL is expected, as more than 70 % of ash elements are found in the solid (Conti et al., 2020), while only K and Na ions are mainly found in the aqueous fraction (Matayeva et al., 2022). Water washing did not significantly alter the material ash composition, indicating that the process primarily removes soluble organic compounds without affecting the content of most inorganic elements. The acid-washing post-treatment reduced the ash content by 3 %, thus indicating that the acid treatment leached some inorganic components from the HTL-HC. This hypothesis can be confirmed by the reduction of the concentration of macronutrients as P, Ca and K, potentially diminishing the nutrient value of HTL-HC-AW for soil amendment application. On the other hand, the pyrolysis process increased the char ash content up to 27.4 %. This effect is attributed to the burn-off of organic compounds, which increases the concentration of inorganic elements in the solid product. As a consequence, there is a noticeable increase in the concentration of nearly all measured inorganic elements in pyrolyzed materials (Fregolente et al., 2019).

The HTL-HC contained concerning concentrations of hazardous heavy metals, precisely 150.1 and 72.5 mg kg^{-1} of Cr and Ni, respectively. This result is corroborated by the work of (Conti et al., 2020). These levels exceed the limits set by the EU Fertilizer Regulation (European Union 2019). For organic fertilizers, the regulation determines thresholds of 50 mg kg^{-1} for Ni and 2 mg kg^{-1} for hexavalent chromium. Although total chromium was measured in this study rather than Cr(VI), the elevated Cr concentration remains a critical concern for agricultural use. In all post-treated samples, Ni concentrations exceeded the limit.

A mass balance assessment indicated concentrations of both Cr and Ni in the HTL-Char beyond feedstock-derived levels, suggesting partial contribution from the HTL reactor materials. The Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL) conducted HTL using a continuous reactor and produced solids with even higher concentrations of heavy metals. The concentrations ranged from 500 to $15,000 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ of Cr and 138 to $6,927 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ of Ni for different feedstocks, including algae, sludges, and forest residues (Middleton-Smith et al., 2023). These concentrations largely exceed typical metal levels in the original biomass, indicating a fraction of the heavy metals have to come from other sources during the HTL process. As HTL reactors are typically made of Inconel or similar

Ni-Cr-based alloys, such contaminations can be suspected to originate from these metal surfaces. Thus, addressing reactor-derived metal contamination will be essential for enabling safe agricultural valorization of HTL-Char, as the alloy selected can leach heavy metals to the products. In this context, future HTL-HC free of those heavy metals could present lower environmental risks and possibly comply with the EU Fertilizer Regulation.

Nonetheless, analyzing the characteristics of the HTL-HC reveals its potential for soil application, due to its concentration of nutrients and carbon. However, some characteristics require careful lab-scale testing and evaluation before agricultural use, as concerning properties, such as high concentrations of heavy metals, have been identified.

3.2. *Hordeum Vulgare* - Mason jar phytotoxicity assay

The effect of HTL-HC and post-treated materials on the GR of cress seeds is illustrated in Fig. 1.

It should be noted that studies assessing the phytotoxicity of HTL-derived chars for agricultural applications remain extremely limited, with only one published study available to date (Sharma et al., 2025). Therefore, interpretation of the present results necessarily relies mainly on the comparison with HTC-HC, for which extensive phytotoxicity data exist. The HTL-HC showed GR values below 75 %. This GR result is likely due to the hydrophobicity of the hydrochar, which caused the sand and HTL-HC mixture to repel water. Despite several attempts to distribute water evenly, a heterogeneous environment was observed, where some seeds had limited water access while others had an excess. A similar observation was reported by Fregolente et al. (2019) (Fregolente et al., 2019), using HTC-HC.

In the work of Sharma et al. (2025) (Sharma et al., 2025), two HTL solids produced from biogas digestate were tested for the germination of *Lepidium Sativa* seed. A negative relation was observed between application rate and GR, when HTL solids concentrations were above 4.67 % w/w. In our work, HTL-HC concentrations were lower than this value (approximately 1 and 2 % w/w), and no negative effects in GR were observed with the increment of HTL-HC application rate.

According to Bargmann et al. (2013) (Bargmann et al., 2013), a negative relation between HTC-HC application rate and GR was

observed in mason jar trials for barley seeds, at tested application rates of 2,4 and 10 % (w/w). In contrast, our findings for HTL-HC and post-treated materials showed that the studied application rates did not significantly affect the germination rates within the same treatment. Therefore, the differences compared to previous studies can be attributed to the lower application rates used here. Nevertheless, HTL-HC application rates should be carefully monitored, as higher doses could reduce germination rates.

Washing influenced the GR in a manner dependent on both washing method and application rate. Acid washing significantly increased GR relative to untreated HTL-HC, while water washing showed no significant effect at 15 ton ha⁻¹ but led to a significantly higher GR at 30 ton ha⁻¹. On the other hand, the pyrolyzed hydrochar at 500°C was the only material to consistently achieve a 100 % GR across all replicates and application rates. This outcome could be caused by the synergistic effect of the pyrolytic treatment, in which the material phytotoxicity is reduced, and at the same time, the obtained material is more hydrophilic, promoting a homogeneous water distribution across the jars. This result underscores the positive effect of pyrolysis post-treatment on HTL-HC for the GR.

The RRI results are shown in Fig. 2. For HTL-HC, it was observed that, on average, root lengths were shorter than those of the control group at both application rates, indicating phytotoxicity on early root development. Similar phytotoxic responses have been reported for raw hydrochars (produced via HTC) when directly applied to growth media, suggesting that inhibitory effects are common in untreated hydrothermally derived chars (Bargmann et al., 2013, Suarez et al., 2023).

The phytotoxicity is consistent with the work of (Benavente et al., 2022), who identified various phytotoxic substances in HTC-HC using PY-GC/MS analysis, including organic acids, phenolic and polyphenolic compounds, furans, and ketones. They concluded that most phytotoxic substances are volatile at the temperature range of 200 to 300°C. Assuming that similar organic compound classes could also be present in our char, it is expected that thermal treatments above 300°C should be effective in removing such substances and reducing phytotoxicity. The higher RRI of our pyrolyzed materials compared to the untreated HTL-HC supports this hypothesis, although the individual organic species were not identified in our work.

Fig. 1. Effect of the application of HTL-HC and derived materials at two concentrations (15 and 30 ton ha⁻¹) on the germination rate of *Hordeum Vulgare* after the 10 days phytotoxicity assay. All tests were performed in duplicate (n=2). Error bars represent the standard deviation. In some treatments, error bars are not visible due to zero variability between replicates. Treatments with different letters indicate significant differences in means, using Tukey's test for $p \leq 0.05$. HTL-HC = Hydrochar from hydrothermal liquefaction, WW = Water washed, AW = Acid washed, PY = Pyrolyzed.

Fig. 2. Effect of the application of HTL-HC and derived materials at two concentrations (15 and 30 ton ha⁻¹) on the RRI of *Hordeum Vulgare* after the 10 days phytotoxicity assay. All tests were performed in duplicate (n=2). Error bars represent the standard deviation. Treatments with different letters indicate significant differences in means, using Tukey's test for $p \leq 0.05$. HTL-HC = Hydrochar from hydrothermal liquefaction, WW = Water washed, AW = Acid washed, PY = Pyrolyzed.

The pyrolysis treatment at 300°C significantly improved the RRI of the material compared to the raw HTL-HC in both application rates tested. This improvement could be attributed to the pyrolysis process, which likely removed many of the volatile organic phytotoxic substances present in the raw HTL-HC. The maintenance of the close-to-neutral pH and combined with the increase in the FC in the material and the presence of available nutrients, could also be factors positively influencing root growth (Hitzl et al., 2018, Benavente et al., 2022). Despite this improvement, increasing the application rate of PY-300-HTL from 15 to 30 ton ha⁻¹ decreased RRI, indicating a dose-dependent response. This behavior is likely related to the cumulative loading of ash and changes in pH and E.C. at higher amendment levels, which can adversely affect early root development.

On the other hand, the PY-500-HTL did not show a significant improvement in the RRI at an application rate of 15 ton ha⁻¹. At the same time, a more pronounced inhibitory effect was observed at a higher application rate. The higher severity of pyrolysis resulted in Char with an alkaline pH (8.4) and elevated ash content, conditions that are known to reduce nutrient bioavailability and impair root growth when applied at elevated dosages. (Suarez et al., 2023, Neina, 2019). Similar dose-dependent responses have been reported for both HTC-HC and HTL-Char, where low amendment rates can promote plant growth, but higher application rates often result in phytotoxic effects or growth inhibition (Sharma et al., 2025, Busch et al., 2012).

Importantly, although HTL is conducted at elevated temperatures (325°C), it occurs in a water environment with elevated water and pressure. Under these conditions, reactive organic intermediates in the aqueous phase and biocrude substances can be adsorbed or reprecipitated in the solid fraction, thereby retaining possible phytotoxic compounds on the HTL-Char surface (Kruse et al., 2013). This mechanism differs fundamentally from pyrolytic post-treatments, in which isolated solids are exposed to dry and oxygen-free thermal conditions. Such conditions favor volatilization and permanent removal of some organic species (Hitzl et al., 2018).

The HTL-HC-WW emerged as the most positive-scoring material in this test regarding root growth. After the water washing post-treatment, the material enhanced root growth, resulting in roots approximately 40 % larger than the control. A significant improvement in root architecture is illustrated in the Supplementary Fig. 2. Although there is no literature

on the washing of HTL-Char, this process has been previously reported to effectively reduce the phytotoxicity of HTC-HC. Breulmann et al. (2018) (Breulmann et al., 2018) reported a reduction of phytotoxicity of HTC-HC applied to cress seeds, when HTC-HC was submitted to consecutive water washing treatments. This post-treatment helps to remove water-soluble toxic compounds, such as phenols and organic acids, which are commonly responsible for the inhibitory effects on plant growth (Bargmann et al., 2013, Puccini et al., 2018, Breulmann et al., 2018, Fregolente et al., 2021). Therefore, the enhanced root growth observed for HTL-HC-WW is primarily attributed to the removal of such substances. In addition, the increased availability of nutrients provided by the HTL-HC-WW, and the possible presence of humic-like substances in the char structure, may contribute to its stimulating effects to *Hordeum Vulgare* seeds (Fregolente et al., 2021, Bona et al., 2023, dos Santos et al., 2020). Although such humic-like compounds were not directly quantified in this study, their potential contribution to the observed stimulatory effects cannot be excluded and should be further investigated in future studies.

Within the same treatment, comparing the material application rate, the HTL-HC-AW was the only material where the application of different amounts of sample did not result in a significant RRI difference. This behavior is opposite to what is commonly reported in literature (Bargmann et al., 2013, Busch et al., 2012). On the other hand, for the other four material assays, a higher application rate of 30 ton ha⁻¹ led to a reduction in plant root length compared to the lower application rate of 15 ton ha⁻¹. Based on these results, for HTL-Char and post-treated materials field application rates of 10 to 20 ton ha⁻¹ seem more practical and less susceptible to phytotoxicity (Bargmann et al., 2013, Melo et al., 2019).

Analyzing the RFW results, shown in Fig. 3 highlights the effectiveness of the proposed post-treatments, as all post-treatments increased RFW compared to the raw HTL-HC. The HTL-HC resulted in being phytotoxic in this germination assay. The application of HTL-HC significantly reduced all plant development parameters studied (GR, RRI, and RFW) compared to the control treatment. A decrease in plant fresh biomass weight when HTC-HC is applied was also observed in the work of Suarez et al. (2023) (Suarez et al., 2023). These results indicate that the post-treatment applied reduced HTL-HC phytotoxicity and enhanced fresh biomass production, even surpassing the control in some

Fig. 3. Effect of the application of HTL-HC and derived materials at two concentrations (15 and 30 ton ha⁻¹) on the RFW of *Hordeum Vulgare* after the 10 days phytotoxicity assay. All tests were performed in duplicate (n=2). Error bars represent the standard deviation. Treatments with different letters indicate significant differences in means, using Tukey's test for $p \leq 0.05$. HTL-HC = Hydrochar from hydrothermal liquefaction, WW = Water washed, AW = Acid washed, PY = Pyrolyzed.

cases.

In the work of Luutu et al. (2023) (Luutu et al., 2023) the reduction of plant biomass was also observed when pig manure and biosolids HTC-HC were applied in plant growth trials. Among many factors, this reduction could be attributed to the labile C fraction in HTC-HC. Thus, microorganisms consume the nutrients to degrade this carbon, promoting a nutrient deficit in the growing environment. The same effect can be observed in our HTL-HC. Since the utilized post-treatments are efficient in removing the more easily degradable carbon fraction of HTL-HC, this effect can be diminished, allowing the plant to utilize available nutrients to boost its growth.

The dried barley plants were analyzed using ICP-OES, with results displayed in Supplementary Table S5. Notably, the plants did not uptake heavy metals such as Cu, Cr, and Ni from the chars. Additionally, Cu concentrations were below the detection limit, and Ni concentrations of all samples were lower than 0.1 mg g^{-1} . This finding is significant as it suggests that the heavy metals present in the HTL-HC were not absorbed by the plants during our experimental period, therefore not affecting plant growth and not being responsible for the observed phytotoxicity. One possible explanation is that the heavy metals present in the HTL-HC and its derivatives are not bioavailable to plants, likely existing in a stable form within the solid matrix (Wang et al., 2025). This hypothesis is supported by findings in the work of (Bona et al., 2023). Additionally, the HTL-Char may contain humic-like molecules within its structure, which can stabilize heavy metals through complexation, thereby reducing their bioavailability (dos Santos et al., 2020). However, in our study, the short experimental duration of 10 days and the utilization of sand instead of soil are insufficient to draw definitive conclusions about the long-term bioavailability of heavy metals in the chars and their potential leaching to the soil over a prolonged period.

Overall, the barley phytotoxicity assays demonstrate that HTL-HC exhibits phytotoxic effects primarily at early developmental stages, as reflected by reduced GR and root length, which are recognized as the

most sensitive indicators of plant stress. This assay also concluded that the most probable mechanisms for the observed growth inhibition or stimulant effects on *Hordeum Vulgare* seeds are due to a mixture of factors, with the most significant being the pH, and the presence of organic substances. Based on previous HTC-HC literature, it is hypothesized that those phytotoxic substances are mainly composed of phenolic and polyphenolic compounds, small-chain organic acids and aldehydes. The classes and types of organic substances responsible for the phytotoxicity will be investigated in section 3.3.

3.3. *Lepidium Sativum* - Petri dish phytotoxicity assay

The produced HTL-HC and derived solids were tested for the germination of *Lepidium sativum* seeds using the nutrient extract method. All treatments resulted in a 100 % germination rate, indicating no inhibitory effects on seed germination under the tested conditions. As seed germination represents an early toxicity endpoint, potential phytotoxic effects were further assessed using RL measurements. Since all assays were conducted within the same batch under identical experimental conditions, direct comparison of root lengths is feasible. The RL results are presented in Fig. 4.

Compared to the control treatment, assays using HTL-HC significantly reduced root length, with root lengths averaging $66.8 \pm 2.5 \%$ shorter than the control. Phytotoxicity of the extract from raw HTC-HC has been previously reported (Lang et al., 2025). The washing post-treatments, using water and acid resulted in improved root growth compared to untreated HTL-HC. Median root lengths in these treatments were approximately twice as long as those with HTL-HC, but still shorter than those in the control. This indicates that the washing post-treatments effectively reduced the phytotoxicity of HTL-HC (Bargmann et al., 2013, Suarez et al., 2023).

The pyrolysis treatment effectively eliminated the phytotoxicity of the material in both temperatures tested. The RL were similar to those of

Fig. 4. Effect of the application of the materials ENS on the RL of *Lepidium Sativum* seeds after a 3-day germination assay. All tests were performed in triplicate (n=3) alongside quadruplicate control (n=4). Treatments with different letters indicate significant differences in means, using Tukey's test for $p \leq 0.05$. HTL-HC = Hydrochar from hydrothermal liquefaction, WW = Water washed, AW = Acid washed, PY = Pyrolyzed.

the control treatment, with no significant differences observed. Thus, pyrolysis emerged as the most effective treatment to reduce phytotoxicity in this assay. These findings are in accordance with the literature (Hitzl et al., 2018, Bahcivanji et al., 2020), which also observed that pyrolyzed HTC-HC nutrient extracts were not phytotoxic, or even plant conditioners, when applied to *Lepidium sativum* seeds.

The pyrolysis at 300 °C effectively removed the phytotoxicity of HTL-HC in both assays, the mason jar (direct material application in the growing media) and the petri dish (application of the ENS from the material). Therefore, pyrolysis has the potential to act as a detoxification treatment for HTL-Char. In this context, a key parameter to be monitored is the pyrolysis temperature, which will alter the material physicochemical properties.

3.3.1. Characterization of the ENS and assessment of possible phytotoxicity sources

The chemical characterization of the nutrient solution and ENS are presented in Table 2. This analysis aimed to investigate potential sources of phytotoxicity. In the analyzed ENS, the concentration of heavy metals was below the detection limit, except for Cr in the ENS-HTL-HC-AW. This finding could support the idea that heavy metals in the HTL-HC are likely present in a stable and immobile form, preventing them from being easily leached into the liquid (Bona et al., 2023). As a result, these heavy metals are not the cause of the observed phytotoxicity in this germination assay, as they were not present in the ENS. Ammonium concentrations in the ENS ranged from 17 to 22 mg L⁻¹ across all treatments. The primary ammonium source was the standard nutrient solution, in which 1 mmol/L of NH₄⁺ was added, following the standard methodology. No relationship between NH₄⁺ levels and phytotoxicity was observed. Therefore, NH₄⁺ is unlikely to be a dominant factor controlling the observed phytotoxic effects in this study.

The highest E.C. was obtained for the ENS-HTL-HC of 5.1 mS cm⁻¹. Additionally, this is the sample that exhibited the highest phytotoxicity. It is known that elevated EC levels can induce stress in plants, inhibiting their growth, and *Lepidium Sativum* is sensitive to salt stress (Busch et al., 2012). Therefore, E.C. could be one source of phytotoxicity in this test.

Table 2
Physicochemical characterization of ENS applied to germination trials of *Lepidium Sativum* seeds.

	Nutrient Solution	ENS-HTL-HC	ENS-HTL-HC-WW	ENS-HTL-HC-AW	ENS-PY-300-HTL	ENS-PY-500-HTL
pH	6.1	6.5	6.3	5.5	7.1	8.6
E.C. (mS/cm)	1.9	5.1	2.1	2.8	3.2	3.0
DOC (mg/L)	1.6	765	80	378	110	79
Phenols (mg/L)	0.0	18	6.4	3.4	1.9	1.4
NH ₄ ⁺ (mg/L)	17	19	22	18	19	20
Ca (mg/L)	157.8	356.1	168.1	341.7	202.5	101.6
Cr (mg/L)	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	0.03	< LOD	< LOD
Cu (mg/L)	< LOD	0.02	< LOD	0.01	< LOD	0.02
Fe (mg/L)	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD
K (mg/L)	328.6	623.8	403.4	322.9	637.1	650.2
Mg (mg/L)	43.0	46.3	48.4	79.5	45.2	39.4
Mn (mg/L)	43.0	46.3	48.4	79.5	46.0	39.4
Ni (mg/L)	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD
P (mg/L)	48.1	49.1	48.1	94.4	40.8	1.8
Zn (mg/L)	< LOD	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.2	< LOD

n = 2; LOD = Limit of detection = 0.01 mg L⁻¹. The standard deviation of the measurements is lower than 10 %.

All post-treatments significantly decreased E.C. across the samples, ranging from 2.1 to 3.0 mS cm⁻¹. These values are more similar to the ones in the nutrient solution applied in the control.

Moreover, crucially, there was a notable reduction in DOC and in the concentration of phenolic compounds. The ENS-HTL-HC had a DOC of 765 mg L⁻¹. After the proposed post-treatments, a significant reduction of DOC was observed for all samples, ranging from 79 to 378 mg L⁻¹. The highest post-treated material DOC was found in the ENS-HTL-HC-AW. This higher DOC concentration can be explained by the chemical effect of HCl on the char matrix. Acid treatment can partially hydrolyze linkages in the char organic matrix and disrupt mineral-organic associations, mobilizing organic components that remain bound in the water-washed char (Liu et al., 2022, Li et al., 2025).

As observed, the reduction of DOC after the post-treatments resulted in lower phytotoxic effects on root growth. High DOC concentration of the liquid extract from HTC-HC has been reported to inhibit root length in germination assays (Bargmann et al., 2013, Bona et al., 2023, Niu et al., 2021). In the work of Lang et al. (2025) (Lang et al., 2025), the DOC extracted from HTC hydrochar produced from several feedstocks was used to germinate *Cucumis sativus*. In all nine tested HTC-HC, root lengths were smaller than those of the control. Although the DOC in their work ranged from 20 to 28 mg/L, approximately 20 times lower than the DOC of ENS-HTL-HC, which was 765 mg/L, similar observations were found in our work. Specifically, germination rates were not significantly affected, but root growth was inhibited.

The concentration of phenolic compounds in the ENS significantly decreased after the post-treatment of the HTL-HC. These trends seem related to the observed reduction in phytotoxicity. The pyrolyzed materials presented the lowest phenolic compound concentrations on the ENS, which corresponded to the highest RL and the lowest phytotoxic effect. The phenolic compounds are commonly associated with phytotoxicity in plants (Bargmann et al., 2013, Bona et al., 2023, Karatas et al., 2022).

The formation of phenolic compounds during HTL occurs via reactions such as dehydration, hydrolysis, and decarboxylation. These reactions can additionally lead to the formation of acids, and aldehydes (Kruse and Gawlik, 2003). The phenols are generated from the hydrolysis of lignin or the degradation of glucose and related furfural intermediates (Pecchi et al., 2022). Thus, those phytotoxic compounds are generated during the HTL process and can be adsorbed on the surface of the HTL-Char. Rivas-Arrieta et al. (2025) (Rivas-Arrieta and Biller, 2025) characterized HTL-Char from cattle manure separated by an in-line filter at reaction conditions, using pyrolysis-gas chromatography-mass spectrometry to evaluate its organic composition. Their analysis revealed that the char organic fraction consisted primarily of aromatic and aliphatic compounds, with phenols, aldehydes, and carboxylic acids also contributing significantly. These findings are consistent with our observations for HTL-HC, in which phenols were detected in the ENS, suggesting that aldehydes and carboxylic acids may likewise represent a substantial fraction of its organic composition. Such compounds are known to be associated with phytotoxic effects (Bargmann et al., 2013).

In the work of Bargmann et al. (2013) (Bargmann et al., 2013), eleven compounds commonly found in HTC process water were tested for phytotoxicity using cress germination assays. Glycolic and levulinic acids were the most toxic, reducing germination to <5 % of the control and completely inhibiting root and shoot growth. Acetic acid, guaiacol, and catechol also significantly reduced root length to <50 % of control. In our study, a compound-level analytic was not performed in the ENS, therefore, although those substances can be present in the DOC fraction, we cannot confirm it. Thus, future work should aim to develop targeted analytical methods to identify and quantify species within the ENS (e.g. GC-MS), thereby improving our understanding of phytotoxicity sources in HTL-Chars.

The observed reduction in phytotoxicity following the proposed post-treatments is therefore consistent with literature reports on HTC-

hydrochars (Busch et al., 2013, Hitzl et al., 2018, Bahcivanji et al., 2020), although direct equivalence of the compounds responsible for phytotoxicity or their removal mechanisms should not be assumed. In the work of Hitzl et al. (2018) (Hitzl et al., 2018) the phytotoxicity of HTC-HC was effectively removed after a pyrolysis treatment and partially removed after washing with water. The study also demonstrated that the compounds volatilized during pyrolysis, when condensed and applied to a phytotoxicity assay, were the source of the material initial phytotoxicity. Those trends are aligned with the ones obtained in this work. These results indicate that similar mitigation strategies from HTC-HC may also be applicable to HTL-Char.

While this study did not assess biochemical plant responses, phytotoxicity could involve these mechanisms. Exposure to ENS substances, especially oxygenated compounds like phenolics, may affect key antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase and catalase in seeds (Gill and Tuteja, 2010, Mittler, 2002). Therefore, those pathways should be investigated in future studies.

The phytotoxicity assay was conducted using the ENS method to enable a controlled assessment of HTL-Char phytotoxicity and to identify potential phytotoxic agents. This approach is a conservative screening that maximizes the detection of water-soluble organic compounds and inorganic species. However, it does not represent field conditions, where soil properties such as pH, sorption effects, nutrient cycles and microorganisms would impact HTL-Char performance. Therefore, future work should include long-term studies in real soils to evaluate gradual release mechanisms and soil-char interactions.

The obtained experimental data highlight that only assessing the concentration of certain substances in the HTL-Char or the extracted liquid is insufficient to accurately predict phytotoxicity, as it is a complex, multifactorial phenomenon. Factors such as the choice of seed species, environmental conditions, growing media, plant enzymatic responses, concentration of phenolic compounds and other organic substances in HTL-HC can significantly alter its interaction with plants. Finally, it was demonstrated that although HTL-Char may initially exhibit phytotoxic characteristics, applying post-treatments before its use in soils can effectively mitigate this toxicity.

4. Conclusions and outlook

Based on an integrated evaluation of GR, root length, and RFW, untreated HTL-HC exhibited phytotoxic effects at early growth stages, exhibiting lower values of all parameters compared to the control. Post-treatments (washing and pyrolysis) effectively mitigated these phytotoxic effects, demonstrating that phytotoxicity was not intrinsic to the carbon matrix but associated with removable compounds. Therefore, we confirm the necessity of a post-treatment step before its application as a soil amendment.

The source of phytotoxicity is likely parallel to that found in HTC-HC, where water-soluble organic compounds (e.g., phenolic and polyphenolic compounds, short-chain organic acids, and aldehydes) are primarily responsible. In this context, the concentration and mobility of such substances can be a key aspect in causing stimulating or toxic effects. Although individual compounds were not identified in this study, they are clearly water soluble and volatile. The identification and quantification of such compounds should be investigated in future studies.

No direct correlation was observed between nutrient content (e.g., P and K) in the HTL-HC and plant growth metrics, likely due to the short exposure times in this study. Future studies with longer cultivation periods, in the order of months, may better elucidate the relationship between macronutrient availability and plant development. Additionally, the long-term stability of HTL-HC on soil, its interaction with soil biota and its influence on nutrient cycles and crop yields under realistic agronomic scenarios remain crucial knowledge gaps that need to be investigated.

Prioritizing the use of HTL-Char for soil amendment and potential

carbon sequestration material can transform it from a by-product into a strategic asset, reinforcing the sustainability and circularity of next-generation HTL production systems.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Gabriel F. Batista: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Andrea Kruse:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Gero C. Becker:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Raw data is available upon request made to the corresponding author.

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